

Q-Switched EDF LASER Cavity using ITO as Saturable Absorber

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Abstract

In this work, we have experimentally reported the generation of Q-switched pulses by using Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) as a saturable absorbing thin film. First, the slide of glass was kept in an e-beam chamber for deposition, and the ITO layer was coated over the glass slide. Then the ITO was exfoliated from the glass slide, over the fiber ferrules in the erbium-doped fiber laser cavity. The Q-switched laser operated on the central wavelength of 1562.6 nm. The pulse width and pulse repetition rate were obtained to be 5.65-4.23 μ s and 48.31-64.52 kHz, respectively.

Index: Q-Switched Pulses, Laser, Indium Tin Oxide, Saturable Absorber, Saturable Absorber Mirrors on Semiconductor.

I. INTRODUCTION

The lasers emitting pulses have gained attention in a plethora of applications including material processing and telecommunication [1]. Passively generation of pulse lasers usually requires a Saturable Absorber (SA), to achieve the pulsed operation [2-4]. At first, Saturable Absorber Mirrors on Semiconductor (SESAMs) were discovered as promising SAs which could achieve stable mode-locked and Q-switched pulses [5]. Owing to the mirror alignment issues in SESAMs, many other potential materials emerged as new SAs which included Graphene, Black-Phosphorus, Transition Metal Di-Chalcogenides (TMDs), Topology Insulators (TIs), organic materials, metals, metal carbides, and metal oxides [6-13]. All these SAs could achieve stable mode-locked and Q-switched lasers. However, they suffer from few drawbacks such as Graphene and TMDs have a low modulation depth, metals such as silver oxidize easily and Black-Phosphorus is a hydrophilic material that is not considered as environment-friendly SA [14].

Indium tin oxide (ITO) on the other hand, has an ultrafast recovery time of about 360 fs and low electrical resistivity [15]. ITO is considered a physically stable material for optoelectronic applications such as LEDs and solar cells [16]. In this work, ITO is sandwiched between the fiber ferrules to be used as SA in the Erbium-Doped Fibers (EDF) laser's cavity. The SA-ITO could produce a Q-switching laser to perform the operation at 1562.6 nm. The Q-switching pulse was stable with a pumping power of 63.41-112.86 mW, and the smallest pulses width was obtained as 4.23 μ s.

II. PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SATURABLE ABSORBER

For the preparation of SA, first, the slide of glass was kept in the e-beam chamber for deposition. Then the socket with ITO target material was selected and the deposition rate was set to 1 kilo-Angstrom or $k\text{\AA}$. The preset of 1 $k\text{\AA}$ deposition rate could achieve a 100 nm thin film over glass slide as shown in figure 1. Then the ITO was exfoliated from the glass slide over the fiber ferrules which were connected in EDF laser, this is shown in figure 3.

Figure 1: Electron Beam Deposition of Indium Tin Oxide

The nonlinear optical characterizations of the SA were done utilizing a balance twin detection technique. The laser source used for characterization was a homemade mode-locked laser working at 1557.7 nm wavelength. The rate of repetition and pulse width of the mode-locked

source was 1.885 MHz and 3.62 ps, respectively. The proposed SA had modulation depth (or the saturable absorption) of 1 %, non-saturable absorption of 69.4 %, and saturation intensity of about 10.13 mWcm⁻². The optical characteristics of SA are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Optical Characterization of ITO-SA

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Figure 3 depicts the EDFL cavity setup which incorporates ITO as an SA for Q-switching pulses generation. A Laser diode with a wavelength of about 980 nm was utilized for pumping the laser cavity. A Wavelength-Division-Multiplexer (WDM) with 980 nm/1550 nm ports was used to input 980 nm from laser diode and 1550 nm from feedback. The ED fiber with a length of 2.4 meters was connected in the cavity as a medium for gain. Then an isolator was connected to push the signal in one direction. The ITO-SA which was exfoliated over the fiber ferrule was then sandwiched between the ferrules in the fiber laser cavity. Next, a 90:10 coupler was used, which allowed 90 % output to feedback and the remaining 10 % to tap out. At the output, the optical power meter, oscilloscope, radiofrequency spectrum analyzer, and optical spectrum analyzer were connected to observe the Q-switched laser parameters.

Figure 3: Experimental Setup for Q-Switched Laser

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

First, the continuous wave was obtained at a set threshold of 15 mW pumping power, before inserting the SA. Then SA-ITO was placed in between the ferrules of fiber. A self-starting Q-switching laser was achieved which operated from the pumping power of 63.41 mW to 112.86

mW. Figure 4 depicts the Q-switched laser achieved using the proposed SA. At the pumping power of 112.86 mW, the Q-switched laser performed an operation at 1562.6 nm which is the central wavelength, as can be seen in figure 4 (a). Figure 4 (b) demonstrates the frequency spectrum of the Q-switching laser at 112.86 mW pumping power. The repetition rate for Q-switched laser at the max., pumping power was obtained to be 64.52 kHz. While the Signal-To-Noise Ratio (SNR) was 52 decibels or dB that shows the lasing was stable. For the pumping power of 112.86 mW, the time domain pulse train recorded over the oscilloscope is displayed in figure 4 (c).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: Q Switching Laser at the Pumping Power of 112.86 mW (a) The Spectrum versus Output Power (b) Radio Frequency Spectrum (c) Pulse Train

The shortest pulse width of the Q-switching laser was 4.23 μ s. The pulse-to-pulse interval was 15.5 μ s which matches well with the repetition rate observed over the radio frequency spectrum analyzer. Later, as the pumping

power was raised as high as 112.86 mW, the pulse became unstable and disappeared with a further increase in pump power.

The relationship of rate of repetition and pulse-width with the increase in pumping power is plotted in figure 5 (a). The rate of repetition improved from 48.31 kHz to 64.52 kHz with the increase in pumping power within the range of 63.41-112.86 mW. However, a decrease in the width of the pulse was seen from 5.65 μ s to 4.23 μ s. This decrease in pulse width and increase in the rate of repetition shows the typical operating behavior of a Q-switching laser. The mean power output and the pulse energy versus the increase in pumping power are plotted in figure 5 (b). The highest achieved pulses energy and mean output power was 12.7 nJ and 0.82 mW, respectively. The current results are comparable to the previous research findings based on graphene as an SA. The graphene-SA could achieve a Q-switched pulse at a rate of repetition of 47.94-67.8 kHz, and pulses width of 9.58-6.02 μ s [17]. The pulse width is comparatively much shorter in our work.

Figure 5: (a) Rate of Repetition and Pulse-Width versus Pumping Power (b) Mean Power Output and Pulse Energy versus Pumping Power

V. CONCLUSION

We have successfully achieved a Q-switching laser by using ITO as a potential and promising SA (saturable absorber). The Q-switched EDFL was performing the operation at 1562.6 nm. The pulse was stable from pumping power of 63.41 mW to 112.86 mW. The highest possible rate of repetition and the smallest pulse width were successfully achieved to be 64.52 kHz and 4.23 μ s.

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Authors Contributions

Prof. S.W Harun conceived the idea of the research study, Bilal performed the experiments and wrote the paper, Faisal and G.Fizza contributed to the analysis of the experimental data and paper write-up, and Prof. Bhawani edited the paper.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest between all authors.

Data Availability Statement

All the data generated or analyzed during the research study is included in this published article.

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